

Observation of zero-energy edge states in rare-earth atomic chains on superconducting Nb(110) surface

Yu Wang¹, David Antognini Silva³, Nicolae Atodiresei³, Felix Friedrich¹, Stefan Blügel³, Matthias Bode^{1,2}, Philipp Rößmann³, and Artem Odobesko¹

¹Physikalisches Institut, Experimentelle Physik II, Universität Würzburg, Am Hubland, 97074 Würzburg, Germany

²Wilhelm Conrad Röntgen-Center for Complex Material Systems (RCCM), Universität Würzburg, Am Hubland, 97074 Würzburg, Germany

³Peter Grünberg Institut, Forschungszentrum Jülich and JARA, 52425 Jülich, Germany

Presented at the APS March Meeting 2025

Abstract

The concept of generating topologically protected edge states by coupling Yu-Shiba-Rusinov (YSR) states in a 1D chain of magnetic adsorbates has gained significant attention, sparking increased exploration of YSR states. While extensive research has focused on 3d transition metals on various superconducting substrates, experimental investigations of 4*f*-shell rare-earth metals remain limited. Rare-earth elements like Gd, Tb, and Eu, when coupled with superconductors, present exciting opportunities due to their strongly localized 4*f* orbitals, which are primarily shielded by outer electronic shells. In this experimental study, we examine YSR states induced by these rare-earth adatoms on a Nb(110) superconducting surface. By constructing Gd and Tb atomic chains along the substrate's [1-10] and [001] directions, we uncover distinct behaviors based on chain orientation. Chains along the [1-10] direction exhibit spectroscopic features at their ends, corresponding to trivial edge states, whereas [001]-oriented chains reveal zero-energy edge states, indicating a non-trivial nature.

Official APS abstract: <https://summit.aps.org/events/MAR-J41/9>